

24,25-Dihydrolimocinol, a new triterpenoid from fresh fruits of *Melia azadirachta*

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Abstract : A new triterpenoid, identified as 24,25-dihydrolimocinol, has been isolated from fresh fruits of *Melia azadirachta*. Zafaral, which was earlier reported from its leaves, has also been isolated from fruits, this time along with several known limonoids. Their structures were elucidated on the basis of spectroscopic evidences and chemical transformations.

Keywords : *Melia azadirachta* L. syn. *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss., Meliaceae, fresh fruits, triterpenoids, 24,25-dihydrolimocinol, zafaral.

Introduction

Melia azadirachta L. syn. *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. (Neem) of family Meliaceae, is an evergreen tree growing in tropical and semi-tropical regions^{1,2} of India and its neighbouring countries. Neem has been extensively used in Ayurveda, Unani, Homoeopathic and other traditional systems of medicine. The tree is, in fact, regarded as village dispensary in our country. Hundreds of compounds have been isolated and characterized from various parts of neem showing pesticide, antiinflammatory, antiarthritic, antiulcer, antipyretic and antitumour properties³. Nearly one third of these compounds belong to tetranortriterpenoids, commonly known as limonoids. One of the popular limonoids happens to be azadirachtin-A which is environment friendly biodegradable pesticide with antifeedant and growth inhibiting at lower concentration. Although all parts of neem, including mature seeds, have been investigated to afford a number of limonoids and triterpenoids but fresh fruits have been investigated, scarcely. In continuation of our interest on phytochemical investigation of medicinal and aromatic plants⁴⁻⁸, we have now isolated a new triterpenoid, identified as 24,25-dihydrolimocinol, from fresh fruits of *Melia azadirachta* along with several known compounds. Zafaral, which was earlier reported from its leaves, has also been isolated from fresh fruits, this time. Isolation and structure elucidation of the new compound are discussed in this paper.

Results and discussion

The hexane soluble portion of methanol extract of fresh fruits yielded known limonoids, limocinol (**1**)⁹, azadiradione (**4**)¹⁰ and its 14,15-epoxide (**2**)¹¹, 7 α -acetoxy-4,4,8-trimethyl-5 α -(13 α Me)-17-oxa-androsta-1,14-dien-3,16-dione (**5**)¹², 7 α -acetoxy-4,4,8-trimethyl-5 α -17-oxa-androsta-1,14-dien-3,16-dione (**6**)¹², along with a new triterpenoid (**3**). Further, the ethyl acetate extractable portion of same methanol extract of fresh fruits yielded known limonoids, limocin B (**7**)¹³, 23-desmethyllimocin-B (**8**)¹³ and zafaral (**9**)¹⁴. The structure of known compounds was confirmed by comparison of the spectral data from the literature while the structural elucidation of new compound (**3**) was done by spectroscopic methods which are discussed in this paper.

Compound **3** showed IR bands at 3400–3200, 2950–2850, 1660, 1380–1340 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of an OH group. In its HRMS it showed [M+H]⁺ at *m/z* 429.4089 indicating C₃₀H₅₃O as its molecular formula. It also gave a fragment at *m/z* 410 for [M-H₂O]⁺ supporting the presence of a hydroxyl group. Its ¹³C NMR showed thirty carbon signals with eight methyls clearly indicating the presence of a triterpenoid skeleton. Since it showed five singlet and three doublets for methyls in its ¹H NMR spectrum, it was evident that it has an ergostane type of triterpenoidal structure. The ¹H NMR also showed a multiplet at δ 3.91 equivalent to 1H which after acetylation of **3** into **3a** shifted downfield to δ 4.82 indicating

that a secondary hydroxyl group is present in the molecule. The $^1\text{H}^1\text{H}$ COSY showed that the multiplet at δ 3.91 had correlation with the signals for H-15 at δ 2.02 and H-17 at δ 2.15, H-17 with H-20 at δ 1.83 and H-20

with H-21 at δ 0.90. This clearly showed that hydroxyl group is present at C-16. Similarly, the $^1\text{H}^1\text{H}$ COSY also showed that the doublet at δ 5.31 had correlation with the signals for H-6 at δ 2.79 which onwardly correlated with H-5 at δ 0.91, supporting that a double bond is present at C-7(8). Five quaternary methyls as H-28, 29, 19, 30 and 18 as well as three tertiary methyls as H-21, H-26 and H-27 fitted well with the ergostane nucleus. The perusal of literature on the chemistry of neem showed that a compound named as limocinol has earlier been isolated from its fruit coatings⁹. The major difference in the NMR spectroscopic data was the absence of C_{24,25} double bond in 3. Therefore, the structure of compound 3 has been elucidated as 24,25-dihydrolimocinol.

Experimental

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained with a FT-NMR 300 MHz equipped with a 5 mm ^1H and ^{13}C (ATP) probe operating at 300 and 75 MHz, respectively, with TMS as internal standard. Chemical shifts were reported in δ (ppm) and coupling constants (J) were measured in Hz. The ESI-MS was recorded on API-3000 LC-MS/MS ABSCIEX in 1.0 ppm solution through MS grade acetonitrile-water with injection mode : infusion through motor driven hardware syringe. IR was recorded with FT-IR Perkin-Elmer instrument. Melting points were determined on a Fisher-Johns melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. Pre-coated aluminium sheets silica gel 60 TLC plates were used to check the purity of compounds and preparative TLC was performed on glass plates of silica gel 60 (20 \times 20 cm, Merck). Flash chromatography was performed with a Buchi Pump manager C-615 flash model operating with two pump modules C-605. Spots were viewed under UV lamp (254 nm and 365 nm) or sprayed with anisaldehydesulfuric acid. All reagents used, were of analytical grades.

Fruits were collected from the neem tree growing in CIMAP experimental farm, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh in June 2010. Fresh fruits of *Azadirachta indica* (2.0 kg) were crushed in liquid N_2 to get fine powder which at room temperature turned into aqueous mass. It was successively extracted with MeOH three times at room temperature and filtered. Methanol was evaporated on rotavapor under reduced pressure to yield aqueous extract (1.5 L). Concentrated aqueous extract was parti-

tioned with equal volume of *n*-hexane three times. It was concentrated under vacuum at 50 °C to obtain *n*-hexane extract (3.2 g). The aqueous phase was further subjected to solvent partition with EtOAc which was then dried on rotavapor giving a puff residue (11.85 g). Both the extracts were worked up independently.

Hexane extract :

Hexane extract (3 g) was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel eluting with the solvents : *n*-hexane, and *n*-hexane-EtOAc in the order of increasing polarities. It afforded several fractions which were pooled into 14 main fractions based on their similarity on TLC plate. Fraction 3 gave **1** (10 mg). Fraction 6 yielded compound **2** (74.7 mg). Fraction 9 (125.2 mg) after preparative thin layer chromatography (DCM-C₆H₆-EtOAc, 1 : 1 : 1) gave **3** (10.3 mg). Compound **4** (86 mg) was obtained from Fraction 11 while Fraction 13 was a complex mixture and was further chromatographed into ten fractions by flash column chromatography over silica gel 230–400 mesh using C₆H₆-DCM, 1 : 1 as solvent A and EtOAc as solvent B. Sub fraction 5 (49.8 mg), still a mixture of compounds, was subjected to preparative TLC (benzene-DCM-EtOAc, 3 : 3 : 4) yielding **5** (7.9 mg). Sub fractions 8 (62 mg) and 9 (49.8 mg) were still mixtures of several constituents and were pooled together. After preparative TLC (C₆H₆-DCM-EtOAc, 3 : 3 : 4), these pooled sub fractions furnished **6** (32.3 mg).

EtOAc extract :

10 g of extract was column chromatographed over silica gel 60–120 mesh and was eluted with *n*-hexane, hexane-EtOAc and EtOAc-MeOH in increasing polarities. As a result, several fractions were obtained and pooled on the basis of their similarities on TLC into 18 fractions. 2.5% MeOH in EtOAc gave a fraction (1.75 g) which after further column and flash chromatography followed by preparative TLC by using solvent system of C₆H₆-DCM-EtOAc in (1.5 : 0.2 : 3.3) afforded **7** (limocin-B, 5 mg), **8** (23-desmethyl limocin-B, 5 mg) and **9** (zafaral, 3.2 mg).

24,25-Dihydrolimocinol (3) : Viscous solid, $R_f = 0.50$ (DCM-C₆H₆-EtOAc, 1 : 1 : 1) ; $[\alpha]_D^{20} : +117^\circ$ (Methanol, $c = 0.0001$); IR (KBr) $\nu_{\max} \text{ cm}^{-1} : 3400\text{--}3200$ (OH), 2950–2850, 1380–1340; HR-ESI-MS : 429.4089 [M+H]⁺

(Calcd. for C₃₀H₅₃O : 429.4091), 413 [M-Me]⁺ (80), 410 [M-H₂O]⁺ (10), 301 (20), 236 (40), 123 (10); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 0.75 (3H, s, H-19), 0.82 (3H, s, H-28), 0.85 (3H, s, H-29), 1.00 (3H, s, H-18), 1.05 (3H, s, H-30), 0.90 (3H, d, J 6.9 Hz, H-21), 0.83 (3H, d, J 7.0 Hz, H-26), 0.85 (3H, d, J 7.0 Hz, H-27), 1.62 (1H, m, H-25), 3.91 (1H, m, H-16), 5.31 (1H, dd, J 3.9 Hz, H-7); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : 34.6 (t, C-1), 19.7 (t, C-2), 40.5 (t, C-3), 36.9 (s, C-4), 50.0 (d, C-5), 22.1 (t, C-6), 126.7 (d, C-7), 135.2 (s, C-8), 42.0 (d, C-9), 40.3 (s, C-10), 22.6 (t, C-11), 24.8 (t, C-12), 47.5 (s, C-13), 50.3 (s, C-14), 37.2 (t, C-15), 77.3 (d, C-16), 55.4 (d, C-17), 16.0 (q, C-18), 21.0 (q, C-19), 42.4 (d, C-20), 16.4 (q, C-21), 31.2 (t, C-22), 27.6 (t, C-23), 28.5 (t, C-24), 35.4 (d, C-25), 13.9 (q, C-26), 14.1 (q, C-27), 26.7 (q, C-28), 21.0 (q, C-29), 25.5 (q, C-30); ¹H¹H COSY : H-7 at δ 5.31 --- H-6 at δ 2.79 --- H-5 at δ 0.91, H-25 at δ 1.62 --- H-26 at δ 0.83, H-27 at δ 0.85, H-16 at δ 3.91 --- H-15 at δ 2.02 and H-17 at δ 2.15 --- H-20 at δ 1.83 --- H-21 at δ 0.90.

Acetylation of 3 :

To a solution of **1** (3.8 mg) in pyridine (one drop) Ac₂O (1 mL) was added and the reaction mixture was heated on a water bath at 70 °C for 5 h. After usual work up it yielded **3** (3.0 mg).

24,25-Dihydrolimocinol acetate : Viscous solid, $R_f = 0.85$, (DCM-C₆H₆-EtOAc, 1 : 1 : 1); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 0.78 (3H, s, H-19), 0.83 (3H, s, H-28), 0.85 (3H, s, H-29), 1.02 (3H, s, H-18), 1.05 (3H, s, H-30), 0.92 (3H, d, J 6.9 Hz, H-21), 0.85 (3H, d, J 7.0 Hz, H-26), 0.88 (3H, d, J 7.0 Hz, H-27), 1.62 (1H, m, H-25), 4.82 (1H, m, H-16), 5.30 (1H, dd, J 3.9 Hz, H-7).

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